

Supplementary Material for "FedSeProto: Learning Semantic Prototype in Federated Learning"

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1 Dataset description

- **Digits [5, 6, 11, 13]:** Comprising a total of 203,587 samples, Digits dataset includes digit images from four distinct domains: MNIST, USPS, SVHN, and SYN, with each domain containing images across 10 classes. Different domains are allocated to different clients in the federated learning setting. Specifically, with 10 clients participating, the distribution is organized as follows: MNIST to 1 client, USPS to 3 clients, SVHN to 4 clients, and SYN to 2 clients. For SYN, each client extracts 10% of the data, while for the other three subsets, each client extracts 2% of the data, ensuring no overlap between client datasets.
- **Office Caltech [2, 3, 14]:** Office Caltech dataset includes 2,533 samples from four domains, *i.e.*, Caltech, Amazon, Webcam, and DSLR, each containing images from 10 different classes. For Office Caltech dataset, we assign Caltech to 3 clients, Amazon to 1 client, Webcam to 4 clients, and DSLR to 2 clients, with each client drawing 20% of the data from their respective domains.
- **PACS [7]:** Containing 9,991 samples distributed across four domains, namely Photo, Art Painting, Cartoon, and Sketch, each domain includes 7 classes. Notably, PACS exhibits significant inter-domain variability, presenting a substantial challenge in domain shift. Distribution setting of the PACS dataset is as follows: Photo to 2 clients, Art Painting to 3 clients, Cartoon to 4 clients, and Sketch to 1 client, with each client accessing 25% of the data.
- **VLCS [1]:** VLCS consists of 10,729 samples, which originate from four domains: Caltech, Labelme, Pascal, Sun, each containing 5 classes. For VLCS dataset, we assigns Caltech to 3 clients, Labelme to 1 client, Pascal to 2 clients, and Sun to 4 clients, with each client extracting 20% data from the domain.

Figure 1 displays sample images from the four datasets, visually demonstrating the variations across domains.

Figure 1: Samples of the four cross domain datasets.

2 Supplement to the experiments

2.1 Implement details

In the majority of experiments, we set the number of communication rounds $T = 200$. Specifically, due to the significant inter-domain dif-

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ferences in the PACS dataset, which make global model convergence more challenging, we increase the number of communication rounds to $T = 300$ for PACS. Across all experiments, we configure the number of clients $N = 10$, with each client conducts local training epochs $E = 5$. We employ an SGD optimizer with a mini-batch size of 256, and the learning rate varies between 0.003 and 0.01. We use Top-1 accuracy as the evaluation metric, with the datasets split into training and testing sets at a ratio of 7:3. Testing is conducted using a global test set composed of data from all domains, as this approach demonstrates the model’s performance across different domains. In model homogeneity scenarios, we evaluate the performance of the global model, whereas in model heterogeneity scenarios, we assess the performance of all the local models, taking the average accuracy across all clients as the evaluation metric.

2.2 Model setup

We designed two model architectures by varying parameters within the CNN network. The differences of architectures primarily manifested in the general encoder \mathcal{F} . Table 1 details the composition of the general encoder in both model architectures. In the model homogeneity scenario, all clients utilize Model-1 as the backbone model. And in the model heterogeneity scenario, some clients use Model-2 as the backbone model, primarily based on the domain of their local datasets. Specifically, clients whose local datasets belong to the SVHN and SYN domains within the Digits dataset employ Model-2 as their backbone model.

Table 1: The architectures of the two heterogeneous CNN models. The numbers in Conv layers indicate output channels and kernel size, in MaxPool layers represent pool size, and in FC layer specify the output dimensions. p and s denote padding and stride, respectively.

Layer	Model-1	Model-2
Conv1	16, 5×5 $p=2, s=1$	32, 3×3 $p=1, s=2$
Pool	(2, 2)	(2, 2)
Conv2	32, 3×3 $p=1, s=1$	64, 2×2 $p=1, s=2$
Pool	(2, 2)	-
Conv3	64, 2×2 $p=1, s=2$	-
FC	512	512

2.3 Convergence analysis

In addition to the experiments already presented in the main paper, we further validated the convergence properties of the proposed FedSeProto through additional experiments. Figure 2 illustrates the accuracy variation of FedSeProto and the comparative methods with the increase of communication round across all four datasets. It is evident that the accuracy of FedSeProto increases rapidly and ultimately stabilizes near the highest levels compared to comparative methods, indicating robust convergence properties of FedSeProto.

2.4 Performance in non-IID scenarios

To evaluate the performance of the proposed method in non-IID data scenarios, we employed the Dirichlet distribution to partition the PACS dataset, with the degree of data heterogeneity controlled by

Figure 2: Comparison of average accuracy variation across all methods as communication round increases.

the parameter α . A smaller α indicates a higher degree of data heterogeneity. The results are presented in Table 2. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed FedSeProto is well-suited to non-IID data scenarios and outperforms all other methods.

Table 2: Comparison of performance (%) on PACS dataset in non-IID scenarios.

α	0.2	0.5	0.8
FedAvg [10]	42.66	43.48	44.08
FedProx [9]	47.98	48.54	48.39
MOON [8]	47.20	47.48	47.65
FedProto [15]	48.22	48.33	48.58
FedSR [12]	46.80	47.73	48.17
FedAvg+GA [16]	42.98	43.87	44.86
FPL [4]	<u>48.28</u>	<u>49.45</u>	<u>49.73</u>
FedSeProto	49.59	50.93	51.28

2.5 Performance with larger numbers of clients

Table 3: Comparison of performance (%) on PACS dataset with larger numbers of clients.

Number of Clients	20	30
FedAvg [10]	47.85	48.23
FedProx [9]	50.87	51.53
MOON [8]	50.53	50.98
FedProto [15]	51.14	51.96
FedSR [12]	50.33	<u>52.29</u>
FedAvg+GA [16]	48.07	48.30
FPL [4]	<u>51.43</u>	52.25
FedSeProto	52.33	53.37

To demonstrate that the proposed method can scale to larger, real-world federated learning, we conducted experiments with the number

of clients increased to 20 and 30. The experimental results on the PACS dataset, presented in Table 3, indicate that our method exhibits good scalability.

2.6 Computational overhead

The proposed method introduces new components compared to FedAvg [10]. To assess the impact of these components on the computational overhead, we recorded the convergence time required by each comparative method. The results are presented in Table 4. The results indicate that, although FedSeProto introduces additional components to learn semantic prototypes, the overall computational and communication overhead remains acceptable.

Table 4: Comparison of convergence time on PACS dataset.

	Convergence time
FedAvg [10]	400 mins
FedProx [9]	410 mins
MOON [8]	403 mins
FedProto [15]	523 mins
FedSR [12]	411 mins
FedAvg+GA [16]	467 mins
FPL [4]	566 mins
FedSeProto	495 mins

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